

Markerless Analysis of Upper Limb Deficits After Cervical Spinal Cord Injury: Preliminary Results

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Abstract—Recent advances in markerless pose estimation, based on computer vision and deep neural networks, have enabled the extraction of human pose and movement information from video data. However, their applicability to neurological populations remains underexplored. To address this gap, we evaluated the performance of MediaPipe Pose algorithm in assessing bilateral arm movements in individuals with spinal lesions. Twelve participants with C5-C7 spinal injuries and twelve unimpaired individuals were assessed using the Arm Stabilization Test, a subset of the "Van Lieshout Arm/Hand Function Test." Upper body kinematics were captured during the task using an RGB camera and a traditional stereophotogrammetric system for comparison. Both methods revealed significant difficulties experienced by SCI participants in maintaining arm positions against gravity. This study highlights the potential of markerless pose estimation for clinical applications, offering a simple, non-invasive, and computationally efficient alternative to traditional kinematic assessments.

Index Terms—Markerless motion analysis, Computer vision, Spinal Cord Injury, Upper body kinematic

I. INTRODUCTION

Kinematic analysis is essential in evaluating motor functions in clinical settings, especially for individuals with cervical spinal cord injury (cSCI) [1]. These injuries often lead to bilateral impairments in the arms and hands, severely impacting daily activities [2]. Accurate assessment of upper limb function is crucial for developing effective rehabilitation strategies, as it helps clinicians identify impairments, track progress, and guide interventions [2]. Traditional kinematic assessments typically use infrared marker-based motion capture systems, which provide precise 3D measurements and are widely used in neurological conditions like stroke and multiple sclerosis [3]. However, these systems are costly, complex to set up, and can hinder natural movement due to the need for markers. Recent advances in deep learning and computer vision have enabled markerless motion capture techniques from RGB video data, which are non-invasive, cost-effective, and can be implemented using widely available devices like smartphones [4]. Human pose estimation algorithms deliver

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real-time performance on mobile devices, offering a practical alternative to traditional systems. While they show significant potential in medical applications, their use in assessing spinal cord injuries has been largely under-explored. This study aims to bridge this gap by evaluating the accuracy of a markerless 3D pose estimation (MediaPipe Pose [5]) compared to the gold standard marker-based system in assessing bilateral upper limb function following cSCI. We focused on the Stabilization sub-test of the Van Lieshout arm/hand function test (VLT), analyzing the normalized joint height from both systems in 12 cSCI patients (C5-C7 lesions) and 12 age- and sex-matched controls. The goal was to assess the algorithm's ability to detect motion differences related to cSCI. We expect this method to provide clinicians with a more reliable, accessible tool for evaluating bilateral neuromotor deficits, helping to set realistic rehabilitation goals and monitor treatment progress over time.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Experimental Setup and Protocol

Twelve participants with cervical spinal cord injuries (cSCI) and twelve age- and sex-matched controls (UNI) took part in the experiment. The data were acquired following the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki (2013 revision) and the study was approved by the local ethical review board (Comitato Etico Regione Liguria, protocol n. CER Liguria: 585/2021). All participants signed an informed consent, which included consent for the data analysis for scientific purposes and the publication of the results. All participants performed the first 4 poses of the arm stabilisation task of the VLT manual [6], typically used to assess bilateral arm movement coordination (Fig. 1). Each participant performed 6 repetitions for each pose.

Fig. 1. Experimental protocol: the four poses of the arm stabilization task of the VLT manual.

B. Data Recording and Analysis

The kinematic data were collected using a motion capture system (SMART DX, BTS Bioengineering). During the test we recorded, at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz, the position of 7 markers positioned on the spinal process of C7 (C), and bilaterally on acromions (S), elbows (E), wrists (W). During the acquisition, the poses were recorded using a frontal video camera capturing at 25 frames per second (fps). With the marker-based system, we obtained the markers' coordinates positioned on the participants' body. Using MediaPipe Pose 3D we extracted the coordinates of the corresponding landmarks (in meters) in the reference system centred in the mid-point of the hips. All the coordinates were low pass filtered over time (Butterworth, 4-th order, 12Hz cut-off frequency) [4] and segmented to detect the onset and offset of each movement from the analysis of the speed of the elbow keypoint [1]. We then considered the relative positions of the keypoints and markers on the shoulder, elbow, and wrist during the pose maintenance in the frontal plane. For each pair of keypoints - shoulder-elbow and elbow-wrist - we computed the "Normalized Height", defined as the relative vertical position between a pair of body joints, normalized by the Euclidean distance between them [1]). The resulting values represented the normalized heights for the shoulder-elbow (nHS,E) and elbow-wrist (nHE,W) pairs. To test the hypothesis that the cSCI participants performed differently compared with the control population, a mixed-design ANOVA was conducted for each pose on the relative height values obtained both for markerless and marker-based approaches separately. The ANOVA included a within-subject "arm" factor (right and left) and a between-subject "population" factor (control and cSCI). Before each statistical analysis, the normality was checked with the Shapiro-Wilk test. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. A Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons was applied to the rANOVA post hoc analysis.

III. RESULTS

The analysis of normalized height (nH) is shown in Figure 2. The markerless algorithm reports similar results with respect to the marker-based gold standard. In Pose1, no significant differ-

Fig. 2. Normalized Height (nH) values for each pose and both approaches (Markerless and Marker-based). Boxplots display median and 25th - 75th percentiles for SCI and unimpaired participants. p-values smaller than 0.001 are denoted with "***", while p-values smaller than 0.05 are denoted with "**".

ences in nHS,E and nHE,W were evident between unimpaired and cSCI participants for both approaches. Both participants demonstrated full extension of the arms horizontally and laterally, with symmetry between the two arms. For Pose2, the markerless approach reported that cSCI participants tended not to fully flex the upper arm during the task, resulting in significantly lower values for the nHS,E parameter compared to control participants. This deviation in Pose2 contrasted with the results of the marker-based study. For the nHE,E, there were no significant differences between the two populations for both marker-based and markerless approaches. In Pose3, cSCI participants faced challenges in fully flexing the shoulders and extending the elbows, evidenced by lower values in both nHS,E and nHE,W parameters ($p < 0.001$ for both approaches). For Pose4, the participants with cSCI were not able to maintain a flexion elbow angle of 90° ($p < 0.001$ for nHE,W parameter the markerless approach, $p < 0.05$ for the marker-based approach).

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study aimed to assess a single-camera, markerless approach for evaluating bilateral upper limb neuromotor deficits following cervical spinal cord injury (cSCI) compared to a marker-based system. The focus was MediaPipe Pose due to its real-time performance capability, even on mobile devices such as smartphones. The analysis of normalized height (nH) provided valuable insights into the ability of markerless algorithms to detect different motor patterns during pose maintenance. The variations in this parameter across different poses highlighted the specific challenges faced by participants with cervical spinal cord injuries (cSCI) compared to unimpaired participants. In particular, subjects with cSCI showed greater difficulty in holding the pose against gravity. These discrepancies were partly confirmed by the marker-based system and aligned with findings from a previous study [1], reinforcing the reliability of the markerless approach in detecting motor deficits. The ability of markerless algorithms to capture these motor difficulties, while simplifying data collection and avoiding potential bias, underlines their potential as reliable and cost-effective tools for the assessment of motor function in persons with neurological disabilities.

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